

Table 1. Amylose content in endosperm of Hexi 4, grown at 5 locations with different altitudes in Yunnan Province, China.

Location	Altitude (m)	Average daily temperature in July (°C)	Amylose content (%)
Shunghshao	2140	18.6	19.8
Kunming	1916	19.8	18.9
Yuxi	1637	20.9	16.4
Yiliang	1550	21.7	16.4
Huanian	1000	24.3	15.4

Table 2. Amylose content in endosperm of mutant lines induced by N-methyl-N-nitrosourea treatment in Hexi 4.

Mutant or cultivar	Origin	Amylose content (%)
Hexi 4	Yunnan	20.1
94YM01 (dull)	Mutant	11.3
94YM02 (waxy)	Mutant	1.0
Koshihikari ^a	Japan	16.5
Nipponbare ^b	Japan	21.5

^aMost popular variety in Japan, has good eating quality.
^bUsed as standard for eating quality tests in Japan.

YAAS Crop Germplasm Institute. So we tried to induce low-amylose mutants by treating the fertilized eggs of a nonwaxy cultivar, Hexi 4, with N-methyl-N-nitrosourea (Table 2). We obtained two mutants, one of which was waxy and the other with very low amylose or dull endosperm. The mutant lines and Hexi 4 only differed slightly in heading time, plant height, and plant type. These lines are useful for improving the quality of japonica rice cultivated in the high altitudes of the subtropics and tropics. ■

Gan Wan Xian 19: high-yielding indica rice variety with improved grain quality

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The Jiang Xi Provincial Seedboard released Gan Wan Xian 19 in 1992. It is a new semidwarf indica rice variety derived from the cross between Hei Shi Tou, a traditional variety, and F4084, a strain from the cross IR2061/Ai Gan Nuo/Ru Wei Tao. It is suitable for late sowing in the double-cropped area of southern China.

Gan Wan Xian 19 is 95-102 cm in height and has strong stems. It matures in 134 d and has high yield potential under good irrigation and management conditions. In regional trials, the average yield was 6.8 t/ha, 11.6% more than that of M112, a local check in southern China. The highest yield obtained was 8.7 t/ha in the Huzhou region of central Jiangxi in 1993.

The variety possesses resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper. It has tolerance for water

Table 1. Reaction^a of Gan Wan Xian 19 to blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper.

Province ^b / institute	Leaf blast		Neck blast		Bacterial blight		Whitebacked planthopper	
	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c
Zhejiang	5	S	3	MR	-	-	-	-
Yunnan	3	MR	3	MR	-	-	-	-
Hunan	2	MR	0	HR	-	-	-	-
Guandong	5	S	0	HR	3.7	R-MR	-	-
Jilin	3	MR	-	-	-	-	-	-
Jianmu	-	-	-	-	2.9	HR-R	-	-
China National Rice Research Institute	-	-	-	-	5.7	MR-S	3	R

^aScored using a 0-9 scale for leaf blast, and a 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, 9 scale for neck blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper. ^bData from the plant protection Institute of each province. ^cS = susceptible, MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant, HR = highly resistant.

submergence in the areas where floods are frequent (Table 1).

Gan Wan Xian 19 has long, slender, translucent grains with intermediate amylose content, low gelatinization temperature, and soft gel consistency. It won a silver prize for its high quality at the First China Agricultural Product Exposition in October 1992 (Table 2).

The variety was grown on 66,000 ha in Jiang Xi in 1993 and has been spreading quickly in other parts of southern China. ■

Table 2. Quality characteristics of Gan Wan Xian 19.1992.

Characteristic	Mean
1,000-grain wt (g)	26.0
Brown rice (%)	79.8
Milled rice recovery (%)	73.1
Head rice (%)	55.3
Kernel length (mm)	7.1
Length-width ratio	3.6
Chalky kernel (%)	8.0
Area with chalkiness (%)	1.7
Amylose content (%)	21.3
Alkali spreading value	7.0
Gel consistency (mm)	76.0
Protein content of brown rice (%)	8.2

Physical, milling, chemical, and cooking characters of some rice cultivars in Tamil Nadu, India

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Growers, traders, millers, and consumers prefer different rice cultivars because of their grain yield and quality characters. We attempted to catalog certain physical, milling, chemical, and cooking characters in 16 rice cultivars commonly grown in Tamil Nadu, India.

Nine of these cultivars are short-duration (105-120 d), six are medium-

duration (121-140 d), and one is long-duration (more than 145 d). All are recommended for the lowland ecosystem. The short-duration cultivars were grown in 1992 dry season (Jun-Sep), and the medium- and long-duration varieties in 1992-93 wet season (Aug-Feb), following recommended practices. Grain was harvested, cleaned, and dried to 14%